

History of the development of psychology

Khudaiberganova Sevinchoy

Faculty of Pedagogy,

Urganch State University

Group 211 Pedagogy and Psychology

Abstract: This article talks about the fact that the main tasks of psychology are to reveal the laws of the psyche, the formation of human mental states in the unity of phylogenetic and ontogenetic development, and that in the Middle Ages, unnatural views of the psyche in various forms prevailed.

Key words: person, activity, behavior, perception, mind, event, feeling, image, process, opportunity.

Psychology is the science of mental reflection of reality, mental processes, situations, events, feelings in the process of human activity and animal behavior. The research subject of psychology includes such psychological processes and categories as sensations and images of perception, thinking and feeling, activity and behavior. The main tasks of psychology are to reveal the laws of the psyche, the formation of human mental states in the unity of phylogenetic and ontogenetic development. In finding a solution to these tasks, on the one hand, Psychology enters into close contact with the fields of biological science, including physiology, and on the other hand, with sociology, pedagogy, cultural history, logic, and social sciences. Psychology is primarily the study of consciousness and self-awareness, which is the human form of psyche. Since ancient times, psychological knowledge has been developed on the basis of philosophy and medical sciences. Greek doctors Hippocrates and Erasistratus knew that the brain is the organ of the psyche and interpreted the human soul as a material part of the universe (based on the materialism of Democ-/shya). Their ideas are opposed to Plato's doctrine of the eternity of the soul. Aristotle developed a system of psychological concepts in his work "On the Soul". In the Middle Ages, supernatural views of the psyche in various forms prevailed. Due to this, psychological knowledge did not develop. But in the works of some philosophers and doctors (Ibn Sina and others) a step forward was made in this field. Information about human characteristics. began to find its reflection in manuscripts and monuments. In the academies established in different countries and cities (Khorazm, Samarkand, Kiev, Moscow and other cities), students

were taught psychology. During the European Renaissance, Leonardo da Vinci, X. Vives contributed to the development of psychology. By the 18th century M.V. Lomonosov, A.N. Radishchev, G. S. Skovoroda, T. Hobbes, B. Spinoza, G. Leibniz. J. Locke, K. A. Gelvetsii, Psychology A. Holbach, D. Diderot made many discoveries in psychology, enriched it with practical information. Psychology became an independent science in the second half of the 19th century. The German scientist W. Wundt managed to equip the first experimental laboratory in Leipzig in 1879. The experiments of the 19th century in general gained special importance in the development of psychology. During this period, a set of methods was used to study the psychological reality: observation, lab. experiment, natural experiment, analysis of activity results, genetic method of modeling mental processes, test, expert assessment, interview, questionnaire, questionnaire, biography, etc. At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, a number of psychological scientific schools and trends emerged: behaviorism, Gestalt psychology, personalism, Freudianism, etc. The teachings of I. M. Sechenov (reflective nature of the psyche), I. Psychology Pavlov (higher nervous activity) made an important contribution to the development of psychology. In Russia, V. M. Bekhterev's experimental laboratory (Kazon, 1885), Kharkov University and N. N. Lange's lab in Odessa, G. Chelpanov's in Kiev, S. Korsakov's in Moscow, later V. M. Bekhterev's, A. Lazursky's, A. Nechayev's in Petersburg, V. Chizh's Yuryev (Experimental laboratories in Tartu, Estonia) had a special impact on the development of psychology. In 1912, the Institute of Psychology was opened at Moscow University. In the same year, I. A. Sikorsky established the Institute of Child Psychology for the first time in the world in Kiev. K. N. Kornilov, Psychology in Russia in the first half of the 20th century Psychology Blonsky and others began to create a scientific psychology based on dialectics. Modern psychology is considered a science consisting of a multidisciplinary psychological knowledge system, consisting of many fields with its own research subject: general psychology, aviation psychology, military psychology, differential psychology, psychophysiology, engineering psychology, space psychology, legal psychology, medical psychology, neuropsychology, pathopsychology, educational psychology, labor psychology, sports psychology, special psychology, creative psychology, management psychology, marketing psychology, social psychology, youth psychology, organizational psychology, religious psychology, family psychology, history of psychology, genetic psychology, applied psychology, experimental The

main reason for the separation of psychology, professional psychology, psycholinguistics, political psychology and other branches of psychology is the emergence of applied fields in its structure. Psychology is actively involved in solving important issues in industry, community management, education system, health care, culture, sports, transport, radio, television and other structures. The achievements of psychology are of particular importance in the realization of individual capabilities and their activation, and thus influence the increase of labor efficiency. In modern psychology, electronic computing techniques, electrical and chemical means are used to study the psyche in depth. In psychology, fierce debates continue around the method of self-observation (introspection). Some psychologists emphasize it as the main method of conducting research, while others recognize its limitations and recommend using objective methods instead. Thanks to objective methods, the material basis of the psyche has been identified, and it has been proved that the causal connection of subjective states with human internal relations is manifested in a single person and in a group. In the world community, in the countries of USA, England, France, Germany, Russia, Switzerland i. t. psychological research is being carried out on a large scale in institutes and centers, universities. In Uzbekistan, Psychology has been taught as a subject since 1928 at the current National University. 1929 The Psychology Laboratory was opened under the Commissariat of Public Education. Later, education in several areas of psychology began to be given to students in pedagogical institutes. In the second half of the 20th century, local cadres such as M. Vahidov and M. Davletshin developed. Currently, doctors of psychology V. Tokareva, E. Ghaziyev, B. Kadirov, G. Sho umarov, R. Gaynutdinov, V. Karimova, Sh. Barotov, A. Jabbarov, R. Sunnatova are conducting research in the fields of general psychology, pedagogical and youth psychology, and social psychology. Training and research work of psychologists is carried out at the bases of the National University of Uzbekistan, SamSU, Fergana University, Karshi University, and Termiz University. A psychological service has been introduced in our republic and its network is expanding more and more Psychologists generally believe that the organism is the basis of consciousness, and therefore it is an important area of life. Psychiatrists and neuropsychologists work at the interface of mind and body. Biological psychology, also known as physiological psychology or neuropsychology, studies the biological substance of behavior and mental processes. Major research topics in this field include comparative psychology, which studies humans in relation to other animals,

as well as the physical mechanisms of emotion, as well as neural and mental processing. For centuries, a central issue in biological psychology has been whether and how functional functions can be located in the brain. Modern neuropsychology was founded in France in the 1870s by Paul Broca, who discovered speech production in the left frontal gyrus, thereby demonstrating hemispheric lateralization of brain function. Shortly thereafter, Karl Wernicke identified the area necessary for speech understanding.

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